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An Analysis of Conflict Experiences of Negros Youth Empowerment Advocates

Joshua D. Eusebio Jr.
University of St. La Salle
j.eusebio@usls.edu.ph

Abstract: This study aimed to analyze the conflict experiences of the Negros Youth-Empowerment Advocates in Negros Occidental. The analysis of the conflict experiences is interrogated and probed in the following areas: (a) the socio-demographic profile of Negros Youth Empowerment Advocates; (b) differential concepts of conflict sensitivity; and (c) the conflict experiences of Negros Youth Empowerment Advocates in the areas of Culture, Gender, and Peace. This study employed the Descriptive research design where the research utilized quantitative and qualitative data. This research used survey questionnaires and in-depth interviews to establish a thorough discussion in this study. The study found out that the profiles of the Negros Youth Empowerment Advocates are still young, but have their organic knowledge, and dwell on the social norms of the society where they learn everything from acculturation. With this profile, they are much more vulnerable to encountering culture-based conflict that concerns the person's individuality of culture. The Negros Youth Empowerment Advocates also experienced gender-based conflict, which concerns gender exclusion, especially in the LGBT sector. They also experienced peace-based conflict, which is concerned with the equal opportunities of all faith sects in the community, where the acknowledgment of faith diversity is not a priority. Last, higher or lower profile standing does not connote a higher or lower concept of conflict sensitivity. This study proposed a program that introduces a conflict-sensitivity framework and adopts conflict-sensitive approaches for all advocacies for all youth empowerment advocates that should be supported by the Provincial Youth Development Council.

Keywords: Conflict; Conflict-Sensitivity; Negros Youth Empowerment Advocates

1. INTRODUCTION

The youth groups in Negros Occidental launched a youth-for-climate-strike campaign against the proposed coal-powered power plant in San Carlos City in March 2019. On that same day, Governor Alfredo Marañon pushed for an Executive Order for Negros Occidental to be a Renewable Energy hub in the country. However, after the midterm election, newly elected Sanguniang Panlalawigan members backed the construction of the coal-powered power plant.

This decision led to the bombardment of responsibilities and advocacy for the same youth group that initiated the youth-for-climate-strike campaign. This instance gave an image to Negros Youth Empowerment Advocates that they are capable of responding to the social realities that exist in the province. Their thriving initiative was caused by the enabling factors from international conventions all the way to the local government efforts.

The United Nations, through the United Nations Educational, Scientific, and Cultural Organization

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(UNESCO), is encouraging the youth in their respective countries to promote the United Nations' Sustainable Development Goals, namely: No Poverty, Zero Hunger, Good Health and Well-being, Quality Education, Gender Equality, Clean Water Sanitation, Affordable and Clean Energy, Decent Work and Economic Growth, Industry, Innovation, and Infrastructure, Reduced Inequalities, Sustainable Cities and Communities, Responsible Consumption and Production, Climate Action, Life Below Water, Life on Land, Peace, Justice, and Strong Institutions, Partnership for the Goals.

UNESCO is joining the efforts of youth-led organizations to ensure the impact of their actions. Supporting youth groups has been a customary commitment of UNESCO, dating back to the year 2010 during the UN International Year of Youth and Dialogue and Mutual Understanding. Every year, UNESCO releases its annual report regarding its partner youth groups and newly accredited ones internationally.

Article 2, Section 13 of the 1987 Philippine Constitution provides that "The State recognizes the vital role of the youth in nation-building and shall promote and protect their physical, moral, spiritual, intellectual, and social well-being. It shall inculcate in the youth patriotism and nationalism and encourage their involvement in public and civic affairs."

Through the National Youth Commission, the commission provides the youth with opportunities to be active partners in nation-building through youth programs and projects, harnessing their potential to be of great service to their respective communities.

In 2017, the revitalized Sangguniang Kabataan Law, also known as RA 10742 (Reformed SK Law), was incorporated as part of the law of the land. It acknowledges the role of the local youth and youth-serving organization in empowering the youth for their role in nation-building. RA 10742 provides autonomy to the local government units to institutionalize the *Comprehensive Barangay Youth Development Program* for the Barangays, *Local Youth Development Council* for the Cities and Municipalities, and *Provincial Youth Development Council* for the Province. The province of Negros Occidental was receptive in accepting the challenge in the implementation of the revitalized Sangguniang Kabataan Law.

Despite the efforts of the Provincial Government of Negros Occidental in organizing and structuring the youth groups through the Provincial Youth Development Council, these groups usually encounter conflict experiences, no matter how promising their projects are. Often, conflict destroys the project's momentum, delays the implementation of the projects for the beneficiaries, and worse, ceases the entire thing.

This study, therefore, sought to identify the concepts of conflict and conflict experiences in the context of Culture, Gender, and Peace among the Negros Youth Empowerment Advocates.

2. METHODOLOGY

This study looks at the differential concepts of conflict sensitivity and the conflict experiences in Culture, Gender, and Peace of the Negros Youth Empowerment Advocates. It is concerned with the psychological dynamics of individuals interacting within a small group. The research suggests that it would be appropriate to use a particular sociological theory called Symbolic Interactionism, a microsociology perspective that deals with the study of meanings within the social realities. These youth as social beings have the ability to create meaning according to the society to which they belong. That notion of meaning is necessary because that is their basis of actions towards or even against the said phenomenon. In Symbolic Interactionism, anything that exists is a representation of something. The meanings are being provided by the social actors. Thus, the meaning is necessary and may have a reality-making effect on people who interact on a daily basis (Contreras, 2016). The Thomas couple coined Symbolic Interactionism where "meaning" doesn't have a parallel existence from any persons who saw and interpreted the instances. Thus, "meaning" is the facts in which different people collaborate and define different instances (Thomas, 1967 as mentioned in Chandler, et al., 2014).

A descriptive research design was used in this study. Particularly, the researcher employed a qualitative approach to research. In qualitative research, researchers use theory as a broad explanation or theoretical lens that raises questions on gender, educational attainment, age, location, race, class, or a mixture of it. The theory appears at the end of the research where a pattern or generalization surfaces inductively from the data gathering and analysis (Creswell,

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2014).

An inclusion criterion was proposed by the Provincial Youth Development Office Designate of the Province of Negros Occidental to assure the reliability and dependability of the Negros Youth Empowerment Advocates. The inclusion criteria are composed of a) well-structured and organized youth groups in terms of their constitution and by-laws, b) the youth groups are in good standing, as evidenced by their active status, c) the scope of their programs and projects is evident in the province of Negros.

The Provincial Youth Development Council provided the list of the dependable and reliable youth groups that were used as respondents of the study. The Provincial Youth Council was designated as the gatekeeper in order to ensure the accuracy of the total participants in the gathering of responses. The socio-demographic profile of the participants, the differential concepts of conflict sensitivity, and the conflict experiences of Negros Youth Empowerment Advocates was the focus. The data gathering was done through key-informant interviews in order to further interpret and enhance their responses. A thematic approach in the presentation of both the quantitative and qualitative data was employed.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Negros Youth Empowerment Advocates Profile

The youth advocates, aged 18-25 years old, manifest enthusiasm and passion to move, inspire, and work in advocacies, especially during these ages. They believe they understand what causes apathy and how to evade or mitigate its effects by joining youth empowerment groups. With that notion, youth within these age brackets, joining youth empowerment groups, are shown to develop their level of maturity (Blaine et al., 1997; Tencati, Kole, Feigher, Winkleby, & Altman, 2002; Wallerstein, Sanchez-Merki, & Dow, 2004 as mentioned in Wilson et al, 2016).

In organizing projects and activities, females dominate the field of youth empowerment. Consequently, this conveys the idea that males are the ones who implement and act as the frontlines of the group when facing the communities or stakeholders. As a result, males gain more

exposure and influence in project implementation. It is basic knowledge that in a particular group, organizers or implementors are only a small fraction of the membership, and the rest of the members work as manpower or do the legwork.

Concerning the emerging gender role, males do a lot of the legwork, while females are the ones who organize activities, projects, and the general programs of their youth groups. There are also advocacies that trigger the inner differential enthusiasms of males and females. In the study of Moras (2017), gender division exists, where males should be in more technical and hard aspects of the work, while females are in educational and support aspects of it.

The majority of the participants were single, indicating that they are either studying or young adults looking for a job. Being married or even in a relationship affects their prioritization, potentially diverting their attention from advocacy and focusing more on married or relationship life.

Most of the youth empowerment advocates are still pursuing their basic education courses. The participants primarily range from college-level students to college graduates. Once the students immerse themselves in these social realities, they feel compelled to continue what they started, even after leaving the university and pursuing their respective professions. Students in school or university are expected to be more critical thinkers and problem solvers, having learned about more social issues in their school and community (Blaine et al., 1997; Tencati, Kole, Feigher, Winkleby, & Altman, 2002; Wallerstein, Sanchez-Merki, & Dow, 2004 as mentioned in Wilson et al, 2016).

For the geographical location where the Negros Youth Empowerment Advocates are residing, two out of every three residents reside in the Lone District of Bacolod City, which is significantly larger than the population of the participants from the component cities and municipalities combined. This data also indicates that there is an issue that needs to be addressed, as the cities and municipalities outside the capital cities and economic centers are being left behind. Efforts from youth organizations to expand their memberships and activities across Negros Occidental are underway.

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The emphasis for the Youth-Organization type of the Negros Youth Empowerment Advocates is that most of the advocates are joining Youth-Serving Organizations. The emphasis is on members who are getting older and going beyond the age requirement provided by the National Youth Commission. This leaves the organization's full roster mixed with young and professional youths. The dominant group type is the Youth-Serving Organization.

Most participants are immersed in the advocacy of environmental conservation. The rising trend and movement for environmental conservation have been brought about by the current environmental issues not only within the province and the country but also by global issues, particularly climate change. The National Economic and Development Authority conducted a baseline study to identify the country's Environmental Performance Index. It shows that from 2006 to 2014, the Philippines' performance is poorer compared to Singapore and Malaysia. In the study, the Philippines failed on the following standards: monitoring environmental compliance, climate change adaptation, environment and national resources law, and grassroots sector engagement in environmental and natural resources (National Economic and Development Authority, 2017). This means this advocacy is driven by data and research and not necessarily fueled by the trends and series of bandwagon alone.

3.2. Differential Concepts of Conflict and Conflict Sensitivity

The Negros Youth Empowerment Advocates have their differential concepts of Conflict and Conflict Sensitivity. Their answers were based on the influence of their profile as this is the major point emphasized by the Theoretical Framework of the Study.

The top concept of Conflict based on the Negros Youth Empowerment Advocates is disagreement among members. This disagreement among members lies on the notion of the impact of a person's relationship with others on their interpersonal and social relationships. This impact may spread to their relationship as a member or a leader of the group. This shows that the literature contributed by Shrethsa (2014) supports the data on the concepts of conflict as far as Negros Youth Empowerment Advocates is concerned. With their own concepts of conflict, this could pose a challenge to

the need to impart the correct framework for understanding the conflict and the correct handling of conflict. As Johann Galtung proposed that conflict is everywhere, the necessity to teach the conflict and peace framework is needed most especially for youth. (Galtung, 2000 as mentioned in Pathak, 2017).

On the other hand, the participants answered Awareness of Conflict as their main concept of Conflict Sensitivity. The Department for International Development (DFID) initiated community development projects for Afghanistan for the years 2002 to 2007. Part of their project management (as project implementer) is leading other international donors and organizations to the idea of conflict-sensitive approaches in their projects. After their implementation in 2007, evaluation from the community says that "international donors became predatory and they became a problem rather than the solution". Despite the initiative of DFID in leading other organizations in conflict-sensitive approaches, the organizations were wrong in their application of conflict-sensitivity in their execution and implementation. (Bennett, J., Alexander, J., Saltmarsh, D., Phillipson, R., Marsden, P, 2009 as mentioned in Goldwin and Chigas, 2013).

3.1. Conflict Experiences

The most experienced conflicts among Negros Youth Empowerment Advocates are culture-based conflicts, followed by gender-based conflicts and peace-based conflicts. The individualistic upbringing brought about by schools, environments, workplaces, hometowns, youth groups, or even advocacy contributes to cultural variations in individuals. Within these upbringings, innate conflicts arise when someone does not conform to our culture. Culture-based conflicts are prevalent and most visible not only in the local setup but also in the international setting. A study about the impact of the refugee crisis in Europe concluded that the conflicts about culture are the most obvious conflict as the Westerners don't show any will to accommodate the Middle Easterners as the right-wing political methods to protect their borders and citizens (Galan, 2018).

The common culture-based conflict experienced by Negros Youth Empowerment Advocates is community culture. This indicates that the implementing group has encountered conflicts within the communities where their projects were implemented. The conflict between the group

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and the community is an example of an interpersonal conflict. Interpersonal conflict is defined as a conflict where two or more people have different goals (Brockman 2014; Cheung and Chuah, 2000; Senaratne and Udawatta, 2013; Hahn, 2000 as mentioned in Lianying, 2018). The difference among individuals ignites the interpersonal conflict. In this case, the group differences versus the differences of the community. Since the individualities clash, sometimes the project halts or ceases to exist.

The common gender-based conflict experienced by Negros Youth Empowerment Advocates is equal opportunities for all genders. Participants were involved because they are part of the group. This consistency also aligns with their concept of conflict and conflict sensitivity, as their understanding is based on organic knowledge. The Philippines' status in the 2018 Gender Gap report shows that the Philippines needs to do a lot of effort in pursuing gender-sensitive efforts most especially in Economic Participation and Opportunity, Health and Survival, and Political Empowerment.

The common peace-based conflict experienced by Negros Youth Empowerment Advocates is faith-based equal opportunity. This conflict arises when there are two or more faith groups in the chosen community and there is a dilemma regarding the distribution of equal benefits and opportunities to the community. These benefits or opportunities may vary based on religious perspectives, practices, norms, or even doctrines. As advanced by Mitchell (2017) it stipulates that sometimes religion functions as a catalyst for conflict where the beliefs of a particular religious person would be questioned, the capacity of the religious person to deliver services despite his different perspective, and the fear of domination of another religion.

4. CONCLUSIONS

First, no matter how promising these Negros Youth Empowerment Advocates are, their pool of knowledge is basically organic and still dwells on social norms; they absorb everything from home, school, and in their respective youth groups through acculturation. Since most of these youth reside in the capital city, they are on the frontlines in facing social issues in the province and oftentimes face political and social pressures so that they can preserve their identity as *"initiators of change"* despite being young, still studying, and single. Second, based on the

initial conclusion that these Negros Youth Empowerment Advocates' pool of knowledge is still lacking on the basis of social norms and acculturations creates a notion of organic knowledge of conflict and conflict-sensitivity as far as their learnings from their experiences are concerned. The true concepts of conflict don't limit to group setups only, there is a transcendental understanding of the dynamics of the existence of conflict, and how to incorporate conflict sensitivity not only in their project management ideas but also in their daily routines. Based on the discussion of the results, their own concepts of conflicts affect the reason for their participation in the conflict, and their understanding of conflict sensitivity affects the status of the conflict and the action taken against it. The necessity of imparting the true framework of conflict and conflict-sensitive approaches is vital in the project management aspect of their youth group in order to prevent the pulling out, cancellation, or cessation of their projects. Third, culture-based conflict being the most experienced among the Negros Youth Empowerment Advocates signifies that there is an issue of the individuality of culture where various factors pertaining to culture can contribute to the culture-based conflict. But as far as microsociology is concerned, culture is a collection of social realities that they encounter and in order to react to it, their culture works at the same time whether to spark a conflict or to pursue reconciliatory efforts. Fourth, gender-based conflict is rooted in the very common gender issues where the vulnerable sector of LGBTQs is not being considered to be a partner or beneficiary of the projects of the Negros Youth Empowerment Advocates. Gender issues are hot topics that need to be considered and this is the mistake of these Negros Youth Empowerment Advocates where the status of the conflicts is both existing where it is still on heat and non-existent because they do not acknowledge the gender issue at all. Fifth, the peace-based conflict on the category of equal opportunities for all faith sects in the communities is quite prevalent. Despite peace-based conflict not being a prevalent experienced conflict among Negros Youth Empowerment Advocates, the relationship between the groups and the community servers if this conflict is not acknowledged. The acknowledgment of faith diversity should be a priority in order to establish an ironclad relationship with the community as far as the discussion of the peace-based conflict is concerned. The sixth and final point, the differential concepts of conflict and conflict sensitivity as viewed through the conflict experiences of these Negros Youth Empowerment

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Advocates are still young and they have their organic knowledge and experience about the conflict and conflict sensitivity. Based on the literature and discussions, you are not automatically conflict-sensitive if you are old, achieved a high educational standing, stay in the capital city, or are a member of a long and established youth group.

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